
Research Article

From Manual to Mechanical: Redesigning the Chicken Cutting Machine for the SME

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Abstract: *The redesign of a chicken cutting machine for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) addresses key challenges related to cost, usability, and efficiency in poultry processing. SMEs often rely on manual labor or large, expensive machines that are unsuitable for their scale or budget. This research focuses on developing a low-cost, user-friendly machine tailored to the specific needs of SMEs. Key innovations include a modular cutting mechanism that adapts to different sizes and types of chicken, enhancing flexibility and output. Safety is prioritized through the integration of automated blade retraction and non-slip surfaces, reducing the risk of accidents and enabling semi-skilled workers to operate the machine more easily. The use of durable, corrosion-resistant materials ensures hygiene and simplifies cleaning, meeting food safety standards. Additionally, energy-efficient components were selected to reduce power consumption and operational costs—critical factors for smaller businesses. The design process involved collaboration with industry experts, along with prototyping and testing in real-world scenarios, resulting in a machine that is precise, safe, and cost-effective. The pneumatic system powering the cutting mechanisms uses compressed air to drive sharp blades with accuracy, delivering consistent, seamless cuts while minimizing human intervention. This system also enhances safety, reduces the risk of injury, and allows for high-speed operation, boosting productivity while consuming less energy than traditional mechanical systems. This redesigned chicken-cutting machine has the potential to significantly improve productivity and competitiveness for SMEs in the poultry processing sector, offering a scalable and efficient solution.*

Keywords: *Chicken Cutting Machine; Poultry Processing; Automated blade*

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1. INTRODUCTION

The technique of cutting chicken has progressed significantly, beginning with manual techniques and progressing to the advanced technology employed in heavy industries. Traditionally, chickens were cut by hand using knives and cleavers, which required trained butchers to separate the meat into the correct portions. This manual procedure was labour-intensive and time-consuming, making it ideal for small-scale companies such as local markets and restaurants.

As demand increased, semi-automatic equipment was introduced to help speed up the process with tools such as hand-operated slicers and saws, which enabled some mechanization while still requiring human intervention. Large chicken processing operations now rely heavily on fully automated cutting devices. This industrial-grade equipment can perform a wide range of jobs with exceptional precision and speed, including deboning, portioning, and slicing.

Modern chicken-cutting procedures have significantly increased efficiency and product uniformity in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). While SMEs may not have access to the massive, fully automated systems used by industrial processors, they can profit from compact, semi-automated devices that are less expensive and more flexible for smaller operations.

These machines are generally equipped with adjustable blades, precise portioning settings, and easy-to-clean designs, making them suitable for butchers, delis, and small poultry enterprises. With technological improvements, even small and medium-sized enterprises can now achieve higher throughput, reduce human labour, and maintain excellent sanitary standards. This enables them to compete in the market while preserving flexibility and control over their manufacturing process, guaranteeing that they can fulfil changing client demands efficiently.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

A variety of cutting machines are used in the small- and medium-sized poultry processing sector to improve efficiency and quality. Machines like chicken breast slicers and chicken wing cutters enable firms to generate uniform chicken cuts, which is critical for maintaining consistency. Manual or semi-automatic chicken cutters are ideal for smaller operations, allowing for perfect cutting with minimal human work. These machines provide control over the cutting process while minimizing manual effort, making them ideal for SMEs that need adaptable, efficient tools (Jiang & Li, 2020).

Tools like the chicken drumstick cutter and deboning machine are designed for more specific tasks, streamlining processes such as separating drumsticks or deboning chicken parts. These specialized machines increase productivity by focusing on complex tasks that would otherwise require skilled manual labour (Morrison et al., 2021). The rotary chicken slicing machine and circular blade chicken cutter enable rapid, precise slicing, reducing the time needed for cutting large quantities of chicken. These machines are particularly useful for SMEs looking to improve efficiency and speed in their operations.

Chicken dicing machines are perfect for cutting chicken into small, uniform cubes, ideal for preparing products like kebabs or stir-fry portions. This equipment enhances portion control and reduces waste by creating consistent sizes. The bone saw machine is essential for efficiently cutting through bone-in chicken parts, such as thighs or wings, without damaging the meat. This machine allows SMEs to handle more complex cuts while maintaining the quality of the product (Jiang & Li, 2020).

The vast range of chicken-cutting machines accessible to SMEs allows them to considerably boost output, improve sanitary standards, and satisfy expanding customer demand—all while remaining cost-effective. These devices expedite several elements of chicken processing, from accurate portioning to specialized activities such as deboning and dicing, resulting in increased output. By automating or semi-automating labour-intensive operations, SMEs eliminate manual handling, reduce contamination risks, and raise food safety requirements.

Furthermore, the versatility of these machines enables small firms to scale their operations, providing consistent, high-quality cuts without investing in large-scale industrial systems (Jiang & Li, 2020). This combination of efficiency, hygiene, and affordability allows SMEs to remain competitive in a fast-increasing industry while providing dependable products that match consumer expectations, whether for home use, restaurants, or retail.

Redesigning a chicken-cutting machine necessitates careful consideration of several essential factors to improve productivity, safety, and use. Ergonomics are critical in ensuring that the machine

is pleasant for users to use while minimizing strain during operation. To safeguard workers from injury, it is critical to include strong safety features such as shields and automated shut-off devices. Furthermore, the design must allow for easy cleaning and maintenance to maintain hygienic requirements, as well as improve cutting precision for uniform piece sizes, which is critical for quality control. Optimizing the machine's speed and efficiency without sacrificing quality allows for greater throughput in poultry processing. Durability is critical, necessitating high-quality materials that withstand wear and corrosion. Furthermore, energy efficiency should be prioritized to lower operating expenses and environmental impact.

A range of cutting tools are used in chicken cutting machines to ensure accuracy and productivity throughout the processing process. Chef's knives are essential for basic cutting, boning knives are useful for removing bones, and fillet knives are useful for slicing. Different shapes of blades are available, including serrated blades that can cut through connective tissues and harder skin with ease and circular blades for efficient slicing. Saw blades, such as band saws and reciprocating saw blades, are used for more difficult operations, such as slicing through bone-in chicken portions. Furthermore, dicing instruments with specific dicing blades facilitate the production of homogeneous cubes for many culinary uses. To improve slicing capabilities, machines may additionally use electric slicers and rotary cutters.

Portion control blades guarantee uniform portion sizes. Deboning blades are needed for successfully extracting flesh from bones. Furthermore, cutting dies are utilized in automated systems to make certain shapes or sizes, and slicing guides help to maintain constant thickness while slicing. These cutting instruments work together to produce high-quality outcomes in chicken processing, allowing firms to satisfy efficiency and uniformity requirements.

The equipment should also be adaptable enough to handle a variety of cuts and chicken sizes, meeting a wide range of customer needs. Exploring automation and technology integration can increase performance and monitoring while adhering to food safety regulations is required for market success. Finally, the machine's size and footprint must be within the restrictions of SME workplaces, balancing capability with cost-effectiveness to stay accessible to small and medium-sized businesses. By addressing these issues, the redesign of chicken-cutting machines can result in increased usefulness, safety, and pleasure for both operators and customers.

In this study, we recommended a revolutionary way for chicken-cutting machines to address the current obstacle of maintaining high speed and throughput while precisely chopping chicken parts, as well as the particularly difficult issue of human energy conditions. This system integrates waste control and hygienic controls throughout the process to promote efficiency and product safety. Designing a robust and effective system that boosts output, ensures precise cutting, upholds strict hygiene standards, minimizes waste produced, and reduces labour requirements in poultry processing operations is the objective of the design of the chicken cutting machine.

The steps involved in creating a project design are shown in Figure 1. Finding the problems that need to be overcome to complete the job is the first step. Waste, safety, and hygiene are among the issues. The problem statement provides some parameters that are used to determine the needs of the product. Cost, shape, size, tightness, and safety were some of the factors taken into consideration when designing the product. The project's design and manner of use are then decided upon by completing the concept design. To test the machine, a prototype is constructed after the design has been reviewed. After the prototype is made, a test is run to make sure the machine works as intended. If the machine isn't working right, it needs to be returned to the idea design and modified. The machine is prepared for improvement after testing is complete and results are satisfactory. After all that, the appliance is prepared for operation.

The qualities of design that will be utilized to complete this project are referred to as concept design. This project is intended to be a machine that rapidly chops chicken. To put it succinctly, the knife will chop the chicken precisely as planned, cutting away waste. The Pugh Matrix is used as a systematic decision-making method for comparing alternative designs (NAIOP, 2021) of chicken-cutting machines based on criteria. This matrix contains three types of machines: semi-automatic cutting chicken machines, manual cutting chicken machines and auto-cutting chicken machines. Each design is evaluated using key design criteria such as cost, design, weight, size, and safety. By assigning weights to each criterion, the matrix enables a comparative examination of how well each machine fits the required standards. Finally, this structured approach assists in deciding which cutting machine design provides the best overall performance. The total scores given by this evaluation can assist in guiding the selection of a machine that combines cost-effectiveness, safety, and design efficiency while also meeting the operational objectives of SMEs in the poultry processing business.

Figure 1. Flowchart for project design and implementation.

When designing a chicken cutting machine, selecting appropriate materials is critical to ensure longevity, hygiene, and best performance. Stainless steel is frequently used due to its corrosion resistance, durability, and simplicity of cleaning, making it suitable for blades, frames, and food-contact surfaces (Bishop & Kauffman, 2019). Food-grade plastics are also widely utilized since they are lightweight and resistant to moisture and chemicals, making them ideal for components such as handles and guards. Aluminium provides a strong and lightweight alternative for machine frames where weight reduction is critical without sacrificing structural integrity (Smith et al., 2020). Carbon steel is preferred for cutting edges due to its sharpness and endurance; however, it does require protective coatings to prevent rust.

Rubber or silicone materials might provide flexibility and grip, which improves operational safety. Glass Reinforced Plastic (GRP) and composite materials are other viable possibilities, as they have good strength-to-weight ratios and wear resistance, making them appropriate for a variety of non-structural components (Jones & Roberts, 2021). By carefully selecting these materials, manufacturers can design chicken-cutting machines that are not only efficient but also safe and comply with food safety requirements.

3. FINDINGS

The Pugh Matrix in Table 1 compares three types of chicken cutting machines: semi-automatic, manual, and automatic. Each design is evaluated using five important criteria: cost, design, weight, size, and safety, with weightings indicating their importance. The final drawing was picked based on Table 1 as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Table 1. Pugh Matrix.

Design Criteria	Weighting	Semi-Auto Cutting Chicken Machine	Manual Cutting Chicken Machine	Auto Cutting Chicken Machine
Cost	5	3	2	5
Design	3	3	1	2
Weight	3	2	3	1
Size	4	3	4	2
Safety	5	4	1	5
Total Score		62	52	58

Figure 2. Cutting Chicken Machine powered by using Pneumatic System.

Figure 3. A pneumatic circuit used in Cutting Chicken Machine.

4. DISCUSSION

The semi-auto-cutting chicken machine achieved the highest total score of 62, indicating that it performed well across all parameters, particularly safety and cost. The auto-cutting chicken machine follows closely behind with a score of 58, demonstrating economic and safety advantages. Meanwhile, the manual-cutting chicken machine received the lowest score of 52, owing to its poor performance in design and safety. This review concludes that, while all machines have advantages, the semi-automatic alternative is the best choice for balancing cost-effectiveness, safety, and design quality in chicken cutting processes. The final drawing was picked based on Table 1.

Based on Figure 2, the cutting chicken machine powered by Pneumatic has several benefits that improve its efficiency and effectiveness in poultry processing. One of the primary advantages is its capacity to eliminate waste during the cutting process, increasing resource efficiency. Furthermore, it saves time by accelerating procedures, resulting in faster and more productive workflows. The machine is designed to be simple, making it accessible to users of all skill levels. Furthermore, it ensures greater cleanliness and compliance with food hygiene requirements. The cutting machine also improves labor efficiency by needing fewer people, which optimizes workforce allocation and lowers labor expenses. Importantly, it improves user safety by reducing the likelihood of accidents during operation. Collectively, these benefits make the cutting chicken machine a valuable tool in food processing, significantly improving efficiency, safety, and hygiene in poultry preparation.

Based on Figure 3, the cutting chicken machine is powered by a Pneumatic. The figure shows that compressed air is used in pneumatic systems to power a variety of components, including motors, valves, and actuators. Generally, a compressor or pump compresses the air, which is then held in a tank and sent to various areas of the machine via a network of tubes and valves. Pneumatic actuators, which may move parts like pistons or cylinders, are forced when compressed air is released. A chicken cutting machine uses pneumatic cylinders that force blades into the chicken, precisely regulated by valves and pressure regulators

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, a variety of advantages that improve food safety and operational effectiveness make the cutting chicken machine a noteworthy development in the poultry processing industry. The device streamlines the cutting process, saving time and minimizing waste, enabling firms to maximize production while upholding strict hygiene standards. Its intuitive design reduces the requirement for a large workforce while guaranteeing accessibility for operators of all skill levels. Furthermore, promoting a safe working environment and reducing accidents are made possible by the machine's emphasis on user safety. All in all, the cutting chicken machine not only satisfies the requirements of contemporary food processing but also establishes itself as an essential resource for companies seeking to raise the calibre of their output and increase operational efficacy.

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